

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION THEORY - AN INTRODUCTION TO THE INTRINSIC BASIS AND REFLECTION OF KRASHEN'S LANGUAGE MONITORING THEORY

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Abstract

This paper introduces five hypotheses of Krashen's language monitoring theory and reflects on their content, underlying rationale, and implications. In general, the controversy over Krashen's monitoring theory has focused on his "acquisition and learning hypothesis" and "comprehensible input". In fact, Krashen's attempt to establish a complete and self-consistent logical system at the levels of language input, internal mechanisms, and output is a reversal of the "strong interface theory" of the behaviorist paradigm, and completes a major shift in second language teaching from a focus on form to a focus on meaning.

Keywords: Krashen; Monitoring Theory; Comprehensible Input

Stephen Krashen, a leading contemporary American linguist, has been refining and transforming his Monitor Theory from 1978 to 1980. The Monitor Theory consists of five hypotheses - the acquisition and learning hypothesis, the natural acquisition order hypothesis, the monitor hypothesis, and the monitoring hypothesis. (The acquisition and learning hypothesis, the natural acquisition order hypothesis, the monitor hypothesis, the input hypothesis, and the affective filter hypothesis have been in place since its inception. Since its inception, this theoretical model has been controversial. However, it has to be admitted that language monitoring theory was one of the most influential theories of second language acquisition from the 1970s to the 1980s, and it has been an important source of inspiration for language teaching and learning, and an important part of the field of second language acquisition. In this paper, we focus on this theory, its main elements and internal rationale, and try to discuss some of its limitations.

1. Five Hypothesis

1.1 acquisition and learning hypothesis

The acquisition and learning hypothesis is the first and most basic of the five hypotheses. According to Krashen, adult second language learners have two independent ways of acquiring a second language, including language proficiency and internalization of the target language, which are different in terms of definition, acquisition, mental processes, types of knowledge acquired, and roles, respectively, "acquisition" and "learning". Learners in their natural state generally do not learn language rules intentionally, but use the language instinctively for communication, just as children learn their native language, which they naturally pick up in communication with others. Thus, "acquisition" refers to the subconscious, informal learning of a language in its natural state, while "learning" is the opposite, the conscious, formal learning of a language, in which the learner acquires "metalinguage knowledge". In contrast, "learning" is conscious, formal language learning, where the learner acquires "metalinguage knowledge," such as grammatical rules. Walker (1989)

argues that "acquisition" and "learning" at different stages of second language learners are as follows:

Acquisition and learning are the core concepts of Krashen's language monitoring model. He argues that the two processes of acquisition and learning are not interchangeable; in other words, the knowledge acquired by these two means is independent of each other, i.e., the so-called "non-interface position". (non-interface position). Conceptually, a second language can be acquired through "acquisition," the implicit input from natural communication, but the "learning" of a language does not improve communicative competence; it is limited to the revision and monitoring of the language. Seliger (1979) investigated this idea by asking learners to describe pictures in the classroom and observe the use of the prepositions *a* and *an*. Seliger (1979) investigated this idea by asking learners to describe pictures in class and observe their use of the articles *a* and *an*, and then asking them to state the rules of article usage, and found that their actual language use did not correlate with their meta-linguistic knowledge.

1.2 natural acquisition order hypothesis

For this hypothesis, Krashen argues that learners' acquisition of knowledge of language structures follows a specific natural order that is not disturbed by the order of the learning system, is predictable, and is independent of the learners' age, native language background, etc. In simple terms, learners acquire some rules more quickly and others more slowly, e.g., native speakers of English generally learn the progressive *-ing*

form first, then the past -ed form, the plural -s form first, then the third person singular -s form, and finally the possessive 's' form of nouns. Krashen explains that this phenomenon is universal and does not differ between second language learners who have not experienced formal classroom instruction and formal learners.

In Krashen's view, classroom instruction cannot change the natural order of acquisition, and the acquisition process can only be reflected in immediate verbal expression. Comenius' Grand Theory of Instruction argues that "within all natural acts, development is endogenous; a bird learns to fly, a fish learns to swim, a beast learns to run, without any compulsion." It can be seen that he believed that all things develop by their internal causes and order, a view that is similar to the natural order of acquisition.

1.3 monitor hypothesis

Monitoring means that second language learners rely on their "learned" knowledge of the language to monitor and correct the output form of the language. The main purpose is to make the learner consciously judge and adjust the form of the language before speaking, and to watch for the correctness of his or her language. This process of judging, noticing, and adjusting is the process of monitoring. The hypothesis is that speech production comes from "acquired" knowledge, and that "learned" knowledge is equivalent to a monitor, a tool for consciously monitoring language output, editing and changing or correcting it. This monitoring can occur before, between, or after language output. Krashen also recognizes that linguistic monitoring also occurs when "acquired" knowledge is used, but this monitoring is not based on meta-linguistic knowledge, but rather on editing by feel, what we call linguistic sense in everyday life.

Krashen divides the use of monitoring into three types: first, "monitor over-users," who usually use more accurate forms of language but focus too much on the form, resulting in low acquisition rates or stuttering and lack of meaning. Second, monitor under-users, who rely entirely on "acquired" abilities, are usually very talkative and fluent in verbal expressions, with a large number of errors associated with the delivery of information, and are less likely to be subject to the interference and influence caused by the correction of errors. Thirdly, there are the "optimal monitor-users," who correct the language output in a timely and grammatically correct manner to ensure proper communication.

In practice, monitoring of language output, although abundant, has a limited function. It requires that learners have sufficient time, that they focus on the form rather than the meaning of the language, and that they understand the rules of the language.

1.4 input hypothesis

According to Krashen (1982), the input hypothesis is a central part of his entire theory of acquisition because it answers one of the most important questions - how do people actually acquire a language? The hy-

pothesis states that "a condition for second language acquisition to occur is that the learner needs a little more linguistic input than his current level." This depends on providing the learner with access to "comprehensible input", i.e. input that is slightly more difficult than the learner's current level of language skill, and that focuses the learner's attention on comprehension of meaning or information rather than on formal comprehension. Assuming that i represents the current level of acquisition and $i + 1$ represents the part that is slightly above, the comprehensible genus is " $i + 1$," meaning that the learner should be able to understand most of the existing input, but still need to make a little effort to reach the higher "apples."

The ideal input, according to Krashen, is not only comprehensible, but also interesting and relevant. Moreover, the ultimate goal of language acquisition, which is not grammatically sequenced, requires a sufficient amount of input to submit to communicative language use through extensive reading and conversation. In his view, "speaking" is the result of acquisition, not the cause or motivation of acquisition. The comprehensible input hypothesis can be found in the external environment to explain how second language acquisition occurs and the conditions under which it occurs.

1.5 affective filter hypothesis

Krashen argues that learners develop an "affective filter" during language acquisition, in which affect acts as a filter to influence the amount of linguistic input, i.e., the absorption of "comprehensible input". Affective factors that influence acquisition include motivation, anxiety, and self-confidence, and although these are not directly causally related to second language acquisition, they do have either positive or negative effects. If learners have positive emotions, they can facilitate the absorption of more verbal input and internalize it in the brain, and vice versa, creating a mental block. The "affective filter" may be caused by asking students to speak too early or by repeatedly correcting their mistakes too early so that they lose their self-confidence.

According to this hypothesis, the strength of a foreign language learner's affective filter varies from person to person. One reason for the differences between individual learners may be the amount of comprehensible language input they receive, and another reason may be the different emotional factors at work in the learners. Therefore, in order to reduce the negative effects of "affective filtering", teachers should provide a relatively relaxed and fun learning environment as much as possible, so that students pay more attention to the meaning of language expressions rather than to the superficial forms.

2. The intrinsic basis and significance of language monitoring theory

Krashen's model is based on studies of first language acquisition, in which motherese and caretaker talk in children's acquisition of language provide important arguments for Krashen's theory. Mayer & Tronick report that at about 5 months of age, infants can respond to changes in the intonation of their mothers' speech and to the completion of grammatical clauses,

and that mothers adjust the number of "sequential" signals they have sent in response to the children's responses. At this point, the mother's words can be described as the prototype of Child-directed language, or in Krashen's words, "janitor language. The mother's words are an unconscious simplification for the child's comprehension and reproduction, and these words are communicative in purpose and are a very effective and comprehensible form of language input for the child. To a certain extent, the moderate linguistic simplifications made by native speakers to foreigners, i.e., "foreign talk," which is slower and has a simpler structure, also largely enhance the comprehensibility of language input for second language learners.

Mothers and children, native speakers and foreigners actually use a mixture of sentences at both levels - i-level and i+1-level - in the actual communication process. This input, on the one hand, gives the language learner a correct syntactic framework and, on the other hand, provides clear information while reducing difficulty, showing a tendency to move progressively up to the native level and facilitating the further development of the language learner's language skills. i-level sentences solidify the basic communication platform, while i + 1 level sentences create more room for the language learner to grow in proficiency. Moreover, as the language learner progresses, the "janitor language" and "foreigner talk" around him/her will disappear.

The "natural order of acquisition hypothesis" suggests a sequence of language acquisition, but it does not address the process of language acquisition. It is worthwhile to draw on the concept of "language acquisition mechanism (LAD)" proposed by Chomsky and other scholars in the 1970s - that humans are born with "a common language mechanism in the brain. The concept of LAD was introduced by Chomsky and others in the 1970s - that humans are born with "a general language mechanism in the brain". This mechanism contains universal human language features. Language enters the brain and is first processed by the "language acquisition mechanism", which processes the innate language structure and transforms language input into language output. At the same time, the constant enrichment of language input contributes to the maturation of language acquisition mechanisms. As a result, the acquisition of language knowledge must, of course, be preceded by easily acquired knowledge and followed by hard-to-acquire knowledge.

Krashen suggests that the process of comprehensible input requires a period of silence, i.e., a period when children are not yet able to speak. During the silent period, the child cannot speak but can process and organize the comprehensible input and, after the silent period, seems to subconsciously acquire the input language, gradually accelerating the process of language acquisition. Adults also need a process of accumulation, digestion and absorption to learn a second language, so comprehensible "listening" is essential to the process of second language acquisition.

Krashen's "monitoring theory" is based on Chomsky's universal grammar theory. "More precisely, input is the basic environmental factor. The learner does not simply acquire what he hears - the contribution of the

internal language processor (Chomsky's LAD) to acquisition is important. Not all input received by the acquirer becomes the material for acquisition, and for the input that does become the material for acquisition, the language acquisition mechanism itself generates rules that may apply according to an inherent procedure". Some scholars have even pointed out that in "monitoring theory" it is the universal grammar, not comprehensible input, that makes second language acquisition possible.

3. A Reflection on Krashen's Theory of Language Monitoring

From a theoretical point of view, Krashen's monitoring model is undoubtedly a subversion of the "strong interface theory" of the behaviorist paradigm, just as Chomsky's transformation of the generative grammar paradigm is an objection to Skinner's behaviorist paradigm. From this starting point, he has succeeded in arguing for his logical system at the level of linguistic input, internal mechanisms, and output.

Criticism of Krashen's theory has focused on the core of his theory, namely, the "acquisition and learning hypothesis" and the "input hypothesis". It is generally believed that the theory of language monitoring is somewhat abstract and its reliability is difficult to prove experimentally, and there is also an extremist aspect of his theory.

Stern argues that the distinction between acquisition and learning is not theoretically meaningful, because they refer to the same concept -- the difference between them is a stylistic one. We have shown from personal experience that skills learned consciously through analysis in the past can eventually become mechanical and spontaneously used through practice. Second, the fact that "learning" processes can also occur in the target language environment where acquisition occurs, and that learning processes can occur in the environment where learning takes place, does not allow us to simply separate them according to the language environment. Third, second language learners are not only involved in formal classroom learning. In our own case, for example, we often consciously participate in English corner activities, read English novels, watch English TV, and even communicate directly with foreigners in order to improve our second language application skills. This kind of learning is neither formal learning in the form of classroom teaching nor unconscious "pick-up" learning. Therefore, formal classroom instruction and informal learning outside the classroom should complement each other. Fourth, it is not impossible to switch between "acquisition" and "learning". In the process of unconscious language acquisition, we often unconsciously discover many language rules and begin to summarize them spontaneously in order to improve our application skills. Fifth, Krashen's "acquisition" theory is based on the acquisition of children's mother tongue, and assumes that adults acquire language unconsciously, just like children acquire their mother tongue. However, there is an implicit condition that there is no difference between adult second language acquisition and children's native language acquisition. In fact, there are significant differences between

native language acquisition and second language acquisition in terms of learning environment, learning style, learning purpose, and learning process.

With regard to the "natural order hypothesis," it is clear from recent research on language acquisition that children and adults should learn language in a gradual manner in order to clarify the overall structure of the language system. However, the natural order hypothesis proposed by Krashen is, to a certain extent, only a basic discussion of language, but it does not systematically divide people's language learning into sequences, and it is difficult to continue to divide people's language learning on this basis because the theoretical assumptions and methods used in the study of the order of English language acquisition on which this research is based are still questionable. Moreover, the performance of the investigated learners often varies depending on the language task, and it is difficult to control the variables during the experiment. In essence, the "natural order of acquisition" is not the order of mastery of the rules, but rather the order of error rate of the rules that have not yet been mastered in language use. Therefore, it is not necessary to follow this order when developing a syllabus, because the ultimate goal is to acquire a certain language proficiency and there is no need to structure the language sequence.

The most controversial aspect of the Krashen monitoring model is the "comprehensible input" hypothesis. First, the concept of "comprehensible input" is not well defined. In a sense, any input that leads to acquisition must be comprehensible, and therefore comprehensible input that leads to acquisition is a circular argument. Second, Krashen focuses only on natural unconscious "learned" input, ignoring formal "learning. Third, the input hypothesis overemphasizes input and ignores output. This corresponds to the current situation of English teaching in China's secondary schools, which is often referred to as "dumb English", i.e., students emphasize listening and writing, but neglect the importance of speaking. In the process of actual communication, speaking is often the more important form of output. In the process of language acquisition, input is the means and output is the goal, so it is important not to put the cart before the horse. In addition, the process of output itself is conducive to giving positive feedback to learners to facilitate the correction of some errors. Finally, there is the issue of the "i + 1" model. In practice, it is difficult to implement this approach because learners have different levels and abilities, and it is difficult to spend a lot of effort to determine them one at a time. What's more, the "1" cannot be quantified, so teachers cannot grasp its content and difficulty. How can learners understand language input that is slightly above their current level of language proficiency? The "1" is even more difficult to determine because it depends not only on linguistic knowledge,

but also on non-linguistic knowledge such as contextual information and cognition.

4. Conclusion

It is undeniable that Krashen's theory of language monitoring, even though it may seem biased in parts nowadays, does have a great reference value for our language adaptation strategies, teaching to students' needs, immersion experience pedagogy, and emotional filtering. The real-life phenomena of "wolf children" and "deaf people" also inadvertently support some of these ideas.

In fact, Krashen is not unaware of the contradictions of his theory, especially with regard to his discussion of the distinction between acquisition and learning. For example, he begs the question of Occam's razor in his criticism of the Strong interface position and the Weaker interface position. In criticizing the Weaker interface position, he had to acknowledge the indirect role of learning in acquisition. When challenged by the "strong interface position," Clarke argued that if the "strong interface position" were valid, knowledge of learning could be converted to acquisition without hindrance, and language teaching would become "true" applied linguistics. "Applied linguistics. "The linguist discovers a rule, the applied linguist uses the new rule in texts and writing exercises, the teacher teaches it, and the students learn it." In other words, the division between acquisition and learning is a strategy to avoid making language teaching "real" applied linguistics, and Krashen wants to use this distinction to complete a major shift in second language teaching, from a focus on form to a focus on meaning.

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